

Semi-automatic supervised bare soil pixels retrieval: impact of different classification approaches on soil organic carbon prediction

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Abstract

Remote Earth observation approaches for estimating soil organic carbon in croplands are based on detection of the bare soil conditions. However, green and dry vegetation usually cover agricultural soils, while the time window in which soil is exposed is quite narrow. Several spectral indices have been introduced to detect and discriminate bare soil from different types of vegetation. Spectral unmixing has also been under special consideration to estimate the fractional abundance of each soil surface cover class at the sub-pixel level. This study was to compare the performance of the index-based and unmixing-based classification approaches as well as their integration on discrimination of the bare soil pixels on Sentinel-2 (S2) and Landsat 8-OLI (L08-OLI) single-date scenes from dry and green vegetation within four local agricultural sites, in the Czech Republic. A reference soil cover RGB image representing the percentages of the three cover classes in each band (R: bare soil, G: green vegetation, and B: dry vegetation) was created using an airborne hyperspectral imagery with 2.5m spatial resolution along with the same date ground truth photos taken at the sampling points. A reference bare/non-bare soil binary map was also produced after classification of the reference image pixels to bare and non-bare, with an 80% of bare soil fraction threshold. The bare soil fraction images obtained by applying different

classification approaches on different satellite data were compared with the reference image at 400 points evenly distributed all over the area. Accordingly, the best bare soil fractions estimations were obtained when using the integrated approach (R^2 : 0.81 and RMSE: 0.02 for L08-OLI and R^2 : 0.87 and RMSE: 0.01 for S2). Furthermore, bare/non-bare soil binary maps produced by the integrated approach were more accurate than the others (OA: 76% and 85% for L08-OLI and S2, respectively). In addition, random forest (RF) models were developed to predict SOC using sample-pixels retrieved as bare soil by each of the classification approaches. Models performed best on outputs of the integrated approach with average RMSE of 0.17 and 0.14 for L08-OLI and S2, respectively. The highest average prediction errors were yielded by the index-based approach (RMSE: 0.24 and 0.20 for L08-OLI and S2, respectively). Considering all approaches, results obtained on S2 data were more accurate than those delivered on L08-OLI. In conclusion, classification of soil cover using the integrated approach led to more accurate extraction of bare soil and higher performance SOC prediction models, on both types of satellite data.

Keywords: Soil cover classification, Spectral indices, Linear spectral unmixing, Soil organic carbon, Airborne and satellite data

1. Introduction

Soil organic carbon (SOC) is a crucial soil property affecting its health and quality and therefore security of the food supply chain. Remote sensing has been considered as an efficient SOC monitoring technology mostly using the freely available multispectral satellite imagery such as Landsat and Sentinel-2 (S2) (Ben-Dor et al., 2008; Drusch et al., 2012; Vaudour et al., 2022; Pouladi et al., 2023). The relatively high spatial and temporal resolutions of Landsat and S2 data have caused a unique opportunity for quantification and mapping of the SOC content within various cropland agroecosystems (e.g. Gholizadeh et al., 2018; Vaudour et al., 2021, Urbina-Salazar et al., 2023; Castaldi et al., 2023; Geng et al., 2024). Hyperspectral data with narrow-band spectral sensitivity, have also shown great potential to describe various soil key properties (Ben Dor et al., 2008). With regards to SOC, hyperspectral monitoring has been mostly done using spaceborne platforms such as Hyperion (Minu et al., 2017), PRecursore Iper Spettrale della Missione Applicativa (PRISMA)(Mzid et al., 2022) and Gaofen-5 (GF-5) (Meng et al., 2022), or

through airborne imaging campaigns with HyMap (Bayer et al., 2016), airborne imaging spectrometer for applications (AISA) (Vaudour et al., 2016), CASI/SASI (CS) (Žížala et al., 2017; Gholizadeh et al., 2018; Khosravi et al., 2024), and airborne prism experiment (APEX) (Castaldi et al., 2018; Dvorakova et al., 2020) sensors. The successful launch and commissioning of the Environmental Mapping and Analysis Program (EnMAP) satellite in 2022, has also provided a unique opportunity toward hyperspectral based monitoring of soil properties including the SOC (Guanter et al., 2015).

The performance of remote sensing in agricultural lands, however, is usually hindered by dry (non-photosynthetic) or green (photosynthetic) vegetation which cover the soil surface throughout a dominant part of the year (Rogge et al., 2018; Vaudour et al., 2021; Heiden et al., 2022). In fact, the crop cycle in summer and winter covers the soil surface multiple intervals during the year and prevents the bare soil imaging. For that reason, it is quite challenging to record RS data devoid of some kind of vegetation cover in croplands and hence, proper discrimination of the bare soil pixels from the green and dry vegetation cover is of great significance (Rogge et al., 2018).

The unique spectral features of dry and green vegetation can be used to distinguish them from the bare soil within the acquired imagery (Dvorakova et al., 2023). Green vegetation exhibits high reflectance in green (520 and 570 nm) and Near-Infrared (NIR) (750 to 1000 nm) and low reflectance in red (620 to 750 nm) regions of the electromagnetic (EM) spectrum. Dry vegetation spectra, on the other hand, shows a broad absorption band around 2100 nm which is related to some structural compounds such as lignin, cellulose, and hemicellulose (Daughtry et al., 1996). Lignin also has an absorption feature at around 2300 nm which can be employed for discrimination of the crop residues from bare soil (Elvidge, 1990). In addition, crop residue causes a general descending trend in the reflectance within the range of 1600 nm to 2300 nm, which is totally different from the bare soil relatively constant reflectance trend between 1600 and 2300 nm (Hively et al., 2018). According to these spectral differences, two main methods have been used so far to identify bare soil pixels from dry and green vegetation: the (i) index-based (empirical) and (ii) spectral unmixing methods.

Regarding the index-based approach, statistical relationships are being constructed using specific spectral bands, and thresholds are being defined for recognition and mapping different types of surface cover classes (Xiao and Moody, 2005). Numerous literatures have already proven the applicability of this approach by employing various indices in different scales (Zheng et al., 2012; Serbin et al., 2013; Sonmez et al., 2016; Quemada et al., 2018; Yue et al., 2022; Stern et al., 2023). The most frequently used spectral index for green vegetation is the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) (Rouse et al., 1974), defined on the B4 and B5 of L08-OLI and B4 and B8 of S2, all in VNIR region. It is a powerful index to detect the sharp reflectance increase around the NIR region of the green vegetation spectra. The NDVI threshold of 0.25 ($NDVI > 0.25$) is usually applied to discriminate green vegetation from other ground covers. For spotting the distinct features of dry vegetation within the SWIR region, Normalized burn ratio 2 (NBR2) (Lutes et al., 2006), has been designated on the B6 and B7 of L08-OLI and B11 and B12 of S2. Many studies have applied combination of the NDVI and NBR2 indices on Landsat (Demattê et al., 2018; Safanelli et al., 2020; Mzid et al., 2022) or S2 (Castaldi, 2021, Mzid et al., 2022) imagery to discern bare soil from different vegetation types.

Despite advantages, these indices have some drawbacks which need to be considered. For instance, some of the indices built on the Landsat and S2 bands, are not able to properly distinguish bare soil from dry vegetation. In addition, NDVI cannot capture the high-order non-linear relationships of the near infrared (NIR) and red regions with vegetation related parameters, such as green biomass. The saturation phenomena which usually happens for pixels with higher vegetation cover or during the season's peak times is another problem associated with the NDVI (Wang et al., 2023).

Spectral unmixing is breaking the mixed spectra of a pixel down into a set of spectral responses of the constituent materials, known as endmembers, and providing some fractional values indicating the abundances of each endmember within that pixel (Keshava et al., 2002). The spectral unmixing techniques can be divided into two linear mixture models (LMMs) and nonlinear mixture models (NLMMs) categories (Shi et al., 2014). A multitude of studies have used LMMs due to their high simplicity and accuracy (Elmore et al., 2000), while the NLMMs, have not

been under similar consideration, which can be related to the inherent complicacy of the nonlinear mixture modeling (Bioucas-Dias et al., 2012; Shi et al., 2014). The linear spectral unmixing (LSU) is based on LMMs and typically includes three successive steps of (i) dimension reduction, (ii) endmember extraction, and (iii) inversion or abundance estimation (Celik, 2023). Least squares LSU (Heylen et al., 2011), sparse LSU (Li et al., 2022), gaussian mixture LSU (GMM) (Zhou et al., 2018) and convex geometry-based LSU (Pu et al., 2013) are among the most popular LSU algorithms reported by literature.

Endmembers are considered as familiar and recognizable macroscopic features like vegetation, soil, minerals, and water which have pure spectral properties. The spectra of croplands pixels are usually composed of spectra of diverse types of soil and green and dry vegetation. Due to the land surface complexity, determination of the endmembers is one of the most challenging tasks during the unmixing of a spectral data cube (Pacheco and McNairn, 2010; Jia et al., 2016). Furthermore, the coarse spatial resolution of multispectral sensors like Landsat (30 m), SPOT (20 m), or S2 (10 m) imagery, makes it too complicated to extract the pure pixel endmembers (Pacheco and McNairn, 2010). There are two main methods of endmembers selection including automatic (such as pixel purity index or PPI and principal component analysis or PCA), where the human interaction and processing time is minimized (Pacheco and McNairn, 2010), and manual extraction where an expert familiar with the study site tries to identify endmembers from the spectral libraries either derived from the known target pixels within the images or obtained through spectral measurements in the field (Pacheco and McNairn, 2010).

Considering any approach reviewed above, complexity arises due to the potential loss of samples which their corresponding pixels are fully or partially obscured by dry and green vegetation. This will cause a significant interruption in the designed sampling strategies and influence the development and performance of the SOC prediction models (Biney et al., 2023). Facing this challenge, several research endeavors have employed multiple images of the single scenes (multi-date strategy) to maximize the extracted bare soil pixels and hence quantity of samples employed for modeling of the soil properties. However, sticking to single imagery (single-date strategy) might be better in areas with significant temporal variations of the soil parameters

content or when there is a need to study a specific feature within a specific date. Regarding the single-date strategy, very few studies have compared performance of the index-based and unmixing-based approaches on the soil cover classification and bare soil pixels retrieval. Specifically, to the best of our knowledge, the comparison between the two approaches has not been made under the context of SOC prediction in local croplands while using the single-date imagery. To fill this lacuna, the main purpose of this study was to compare the performance of the index-based, unmixing-based and integrated classification approaches on single-date multispectral satellite data, to discriminate the bare soil pixels from dry and green vegetation, within local croplands in the Czech Republic. Bare/non-bare soil binary maps were also produced and compared with a high-resolution reference bare/non-bare soil binary map obtained using airborne hyperspectral imagery and same date ground truth photos taken in the field. In addition, SOC prediction models were developed on the bare soil samples remained after each of the approaches and compared.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Study sites and field campaign

Four croplands (Nová Ves nad Popelkou (Nová Ves), Jičín, Klučov and Přestavlky), all located in rural areas of the Czech Republic, were considered as the study sites of this research (Fig. 1). According to the World Reference Base (WRB) of soils, the sites are mainly comprised of Luvisols and Chernozems on loess and Stagnosols and Cambisols on sedimentary and crystalline rocks (IUSS Working Group WRB, 2014). Some details related to the field campaigns and sites are listed in Table 1.

Fig. 1. a) Study sites in the Czech Republic and sampling locations in b) Klučov, c) Přestavlky, d) Nová Ves nad Popelkou and e) Jičín. Background is true color composite of the airborne image acquired on June 3rd.

Table 1. Study sites, field campaign and image acquisition dates

Site	Area (ha)	Soil sampling date	Landsat-8 image acquisition date	Sentinel-2 image acquisition date	Airborne image acquisition date
Nová Ves	129	June, 2021	15.06.2021	04.06.2021	03.06.2021
Jičín	153	June, 2021	15.06.2021	04.06.2021	03.06.2021
Klučov	175	June, 2021	15.06.2021	19.06.2021	03.06.2021
Přestavlky	58	June, 2021	15.06.2021	19.06.2021	03.06.2021

Total of 320 samples were collected from the top surface to the depth of 20 cm of the study area in June 2021 (around 80 samples each site). Position of each sampling point was recorded using a GeoXM global positioning system (GPS) (Trimble Inc., Sunnyvale, California, USA) with 1 m accuracy. Five sub-samples were taken to cover an area of $2.5 \times 2.5\text{m}^2$ at each sampling location and then combined to form the main sample. They were then transported to the laboratory, air-dried, ground, and sieved ($\leq 2\text{ mm}$) before the organic carbon measurement using the Walkley–Black method.

In order to find the percentage of bare soil and dry and green vegetation, digital ground vertical true color photographs were taken at each of the sampling locations. A sufficient number of

photographs enabled us to cover the whole area that each sample was taken from. This arrangement made it possible to produce representative ground photos with their centers closely coinciding with the center of the corresponding pixel within the airborne imagery. Some photographs taken of different soil cover classes are shown in Fig. 2.

The airborne imaging was conducted on June 3rd, 2021, when there was no precipitation for at least the five past days. CASI and SASI (Itres Ltd., Calgary, Canada) sensors were used for hyperspectral data acquisition in the visible and near infrared (VNIR; 380–1050 nm) and shortwave infrared (SWIR; 950–2450 nm) regions of the electromagnetic spectrum, respectively (Table 2). The imaging instruments were aboard a Cessna 208B Grand Caravan photogrammetric aircraft.

Table 2. Specifications of CASI and SASI sensors

Sensor	Number of bands	Spectral range (nm)	Spectral resolution (nm)	Spatial resolution (m)	Field of view (FOV)	FWHM (nm)
CASI	72	VNIR, 380–1050	3.2	1.0	40°	10
SASI	100	SWIR, 950–2450	15	2.5	40°	15

FWHM: Full Width at Half Maximum

The airborne hyperspectral data was radiometrically and geometrically pre-processed by Flying Laboratory of Imaging Systems (FLIS) within the Global Change Research Institute CAS, Brno, Czech Republic (Hanuš et al., 2016). Radiometric corrections, applied by RadCorr Ver. 9.3.6.0 (Itres Ltd., Calgary, Canada), included dark subtraction and conversion of the raw digital numbers into physically defined radiance units. The MODerate resolution atmospheric TRANsmission (MODTRAN) radiative transfer model (RTM) was then implemented for the atmospheric corrections. The acquired airborne data was geometrically corrected, orthorectified and georeferenced (UTM zone 33N, ETRS-89) using the GNSS/IMU sensor and the digital elevation model (DEM). By removing the noisy edges of the recorded spectra, total of 64 bands remained for CASI (383.05 - 981.98 nm), while for SASI sensor, 98 bands (987.5 - 2442.5 nm) were finally kept. The next pre-processing step was resampling the CASI data (1 m) to the spatial resolution of the SASI data (2.5 m) and then merging both into one full spectral range of VNIR–SWIR data cube. Finally, the spectral data was transformed to absorbance via $\log(1/R)$ (R is reflectance) and then first derivative (FD) to remove the baseline offset (Khosravi et al., 2020).

2.2. Photograph segmentation, reference image and reference map

All photos taken from the sampling locations were segmented and the percentages of each cover class was determined. The obtaining percentages were then averaged to produce a single estimation for each of the sampling locations.

Fig. 2. Representative photos of different soil cover classes at sampling points within the study sites: a) bare soil, b) green vegetation, c) dry vegetation, d) mixture of all cover classes

A random forest (RF) model was developed using the spectra of the airborne image at sampling points (as predictor variables) and the obtained cover class percentages (as response variables).

This model was later applied to the whole airborne image to produce a 2.5m × 2.5m pixels reference soil cover RGB image (reference image) representing the percentages of the three cover classes in each band (R: bare soil, G: green vegetation, and B: dry vegetation). For classification of the whole reference image, pixels with more than 90% bare soil were labeled as bare soil, while the remaining pixels considered non-bare. The resulting binary map was later employed as a reference for extraction of bare soil pixels on the satellite imagery (reference map).

2.3. Satellite data pre-processing

One low cloud cover freely available standard L1T (radiometrically and geometrically corrected) Landsat 8-OLI (L08-OLI) images was downloaded from the United States geological survey (USGS) Earth Explorer website (<https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov>). Fast line-of-sight atmospheric analysis of spectral hypercubes (FLAASH) algorithm (Cooley et al., 2002) was used for the atmospheric correction of the downloaded imagery. The two geometrically and atmospherically corrected Sentinel-2 level-2A images were downloaded from the European space agency (ESA) Copernicus open access hub. The 20 m-pixel bands of the downloaded images were resampled to 10 m to obtain ten similar (10 m) spatial resolution bands. L08-OLI and S2A band values were extracted at each sampling point and employed for construction of the SOC prediction models. All selected scenes of both satellite data were acquired in June 2021, close to the soil sampling and hyperspectral imaging campaign dates (Table 1).

2.4. Image classification and evaluation

Following approaches were considered for classification of the satellite imagery and hence, selection of the bare soil pixels:

2.4.1. Index-based classification approach

Index-based classification of the satellite imagery was performed using NDVI and NBR2 indices applied on L08-OLI and S2. Different threshold values were considered for NDVI and NBR2 indices (from 0.05 to 0.25, with increment of 0.01) to classify and discriminate the bare from non-bare soil pixels. Optimal threshold values were determined by comparing the classified imagery with the reference map.

2.4.2. Unmixing based classification approach

Depending on the spectral signature, each pixel of L08-OLI and S2 imagery was either pure (only bare soil or green or dry vegetation) or mixed (bare soil + green vegetation + dry vegetation). The LSU process was performed to disintegrate the mixed pixels' spectra into distinct endmember fractions of bare soil, green vegetation, and dry vegetation. This was done in two distinct phases of extraction of the endmember spectral signatures and determination of the endmembers' proportion in each pixel (Kathirvelu et al., 2023). Considering the coarse pixel dimensions of the multispectral imagery used in this study, it was relatively difficult to identify pure signature of each cover class. Hence, the pure pixels and endmembers were manually selected and extracted from the high spatial resolution airborne imagery. To do so, the reference map was used to select fifteen pure pixels of each cover class as endmembers. A spectral library was then established containing 15 bare soil, 15 green vegetation and 15 dry vegetation sample related pixels (sample-pixels) spectra extracted from the airborne imagery. For each of the classes, the recorded spectra were averaged and then resampled to L08-OLI and S2 bands, resulting in a representative endmember signature for each of the cover classes. Abundance maps indicating each endmember's fraction in the satellite images pixels were then produced while considering the non-negativity and sum-to-one abundance constraints for the endmembers (Kathirvelu et al., 2023). Finally, different classification thresholds of bare soil fraction from 50% to 95% with the 5% increment were considered to label the bare soil pixels. If a cover class in a mixed pixel had a bare soil portion over the selected threshold value, the pixel was labeled as bare soil, otherwise, the pixel was considered as non-bare. The reference map was used to find the best threshold values.

2.4.3. Integrated approach

In the integrated approach, NDVI and NBR2 values of each sample-pixel (calculated by index-based approach) and corresponding soil cover fractions within the abundance maps (retrieved by unmixing-based approach) were adopted as inputs of a random forest (RF) classifier, while the observed bare soil fraction (average of the bare soil fractions of the same location pixels within the reference image), was considered as the output. No assumption is needed on distribution of the data when using the RF which is an advantage of this classifier over the other classification

methods such as artificial neural network and support vector machine (Kathirvelu et al., 2023). After training and evaluation, the classifier was further used to predict the bare soil fractions of the whole area pixels. Similar to the unmixing-based approach, different classification thresholds (from 50% to 95% with increment of 5%) were considered to label the mixed pixels. If a cover class had a bare soil fraction over the threshold value, the pixel was classified as bare soil, otherwise, non-bare label was assigned to that pixel. The reference map served as a guide to determine the optimal threshold values.

2.4.4. Evaluation of the classification approaches

As mentioned, the high spatial resolution image and map were used as the reference for evaluating the performance of the classification approaches. Before evaluation, all classified imagery were resampled to the spatial resolution of the reference image and map (2.5m × 2.5m). Linear regression analysis was implemented to compare the bare soil fractions of satellite imagery and reference image at 400 random pixels distributed evenly over the whole study area. Coefficient of determination (R^2) (Eq. 1) was used to explore the strength of the relationship between estimated and observed values, while root mean square error (RMSE) (Eq. 2) determined the estimation error. Since the index-based approach does not yield the cover fraction, it was decided to use ($S_{indices} = NDVI + NBR2$) when $S_{indices} < 1$, and ($S_{indices} - 1$) when $S_{indices} > 1$.

The classified maps were also assessed (at the same 400 pixels) using the confusion matrix and overall accuracy (OA). Confusion matrix is a popular assessment tool to evaluate the performance of classification models. In this study, it displays the number of correctly (true) and incorrectly (false) classified bare (positive) and non-bare (negative) soil pixels, as the true positive, true negative, false positives, and false negatives values. Using the confusion matrix, OA of each classification approach is calculated as the ratio of corrected-classified bare soil pixels (true positive) to all classified pixels.

2.5. SOC models development and mapping

The RF algorithm (Breiman, 2001) was used to develop SOC prediction models on L08-OLI and S2 bare soil sample-pixels, retrieved by using different classification approaches. Modeling was

performed on samples of all sites, separately and together, via the ‘randomForest’ package in RStudio environment (R Core Team, 2020). The Kennard–Stone (KS) algorithm (Kennard and Stone, 1969) was used to divide samples into training and testing subsets with 75:25 % ratio. The prediction models were calibrated on the training dataset using a 5-fold cross-validation technique. All calibrated models were evaluated on the validation subset using four common evaluation criteria, R^2 , RMSE, mean error (ME), and ratio of prediction to deviation (RPD) (Eq. 1 to 4, respectively).

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (o_i - p_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (o_i - \mu_o)^2} \quad (1)$$

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (o_i - p_i)^2} \quad (2)$$

$$ME = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (o_i - p_i) \quad (3)$$

$$RPD = \frac{StD}{RMSE} \quad (4)$$

Accordingly, n denotes the quantity of samples, μ_o is the average of the observation values, o_i and p_i represent the observed and predicted values, respectively and StD is the standard deviation of the validation data set. The higher the RPD and R^2 and the lower the ME and RMSE, the better each model’s performance. Fig. 3 shows flowchart of the methodology employed in the current study.

Fig. 3. Methodology flowchart of the study

3. Results

3.1. Segmented photos and samples statistics

All digital photos were segmented and percentages of every soil cover class were calculated within each sample's area ($2.5 \times 2.5\text{m}$). Fig. 4 shows four representative original photos (right) and their corresponding segmentation (left) along with the area percentages of different soil cover classes. Visual comparison indicated that the segmentation was satisfactory and soil cover fractions were successfully extracted. Samples with each soil cover class percentage greater than 80% were labeled as that cover type.

Table 3 shows general statistics of the samples categorized in each of the soil cover classes and sites. Accordingly, 211 soil samples were considered as bare soil while 69 and 40 samples were considered as green and dry vegetation, respectively. Considering all samples together, the SOC content varied within the limits of 0.31% and 3.97% with average of 1.18%. SOC content in different soil cover classes ranged between 0.63 to 3.97%, 0.31 to 1.85% and 0.5 to 1.87% with the average values of 1.22% (highest), 1.1% (lowest), and 1.13% for bare soil, green and dry vegetation, respectively. In addition, different sites showed different SOC levels within the bare soil category (class), ranging between 0.88% to 3.97%, 0.81% to 1.78%, 0.78% to 1.54% and 0.63%

to 2.13% with average SOC values of 1.42, 1.06, 1.09 and 1.20 for Nová Ves, Jičín, Klučov, and Přestavlky areas, respectively.

Table 3. Descriptive statistics of samples' SOC content (%) in different cover classes and sites

	Bare soil			Green vegetation			Dry vegetation					
	n	Min	Max	Mean	n	Min	Max	Mean	n	Min	Max	Mean
Nova Ves	63	0.88	3.97	1.42	12	1.06	1.85	1.37	5	1.18	1.57	1.36
Jičín	22	0.81	1.78	1.06	40	0.69	1.61	1.03	17	0.5	1.87	1.03
Klučov	61	0.78	1.54	1.09	3	0.98	1.54	1.17	15	0.77	1.61	1.18
Přestavlky	65	0.63	2.13	1.20	14	0.31	1.51	1.05	3	0.94	1.29	1.12
All	211	0.63	3.97	1.22	69	0.31	1.85	1.1	40	0.5	1.87	1.13

n: number of samples, Min: Minimum, Max: Maximum

3.2. Soil cover reference image and map

Fig. 5 illustrates the resulted reference image with each pixel value representing the percentages of different cover fractions (R: bare soil, G: green vegetation, and B: dry vegetation). The image is constructed by applying the developed RF model on the CS airborne imagery, all over the study area. According to the figure, all types of cover classes could be observed throughout the study area with domination of bare soil in all sites except for Jičín. Dry vegetation showed the lowest area coverage, mostly seen around or within bare soil pixels.

The reference map obtained after classification of the reference image into bare soil and non-bare soil classes is shown in Fig. 6. It later assisted with evaluation of the classification approaches performed on the L08-OLI and S2 satellite data. Similar to the reference image, most of the area is covered by bare soil pixels with the highest and lowest dominance for the Přestavlky and Jičín sites respectively.

Fig. 5. Reference image (R: bare soil, G: green vegetation, and B: dry vegetation) for a) Nová Ves nad Popelkou, b) Jičín, c) Klučov and d) Přestavlky sites

Fig. 6. Reference map prepared after classification of the reference image for a) Nová Ves nad Popelkou, b) Jičín, c) Klučov and d) Přestavky sites

3.3. Classification results

Results of the regression analysis conducted between the estimated bare soil fractions and those observed on the reference image are presented in Table 4. In addition, fig. 7 illustrates the scatter diagrams comparing the observed and estimated bare soil fractions. As mentioned in section 2.4.4, these evaluations were performed on 400 spatially representative pixels, distributed all over the study area.

The bare soil fractions estimated using all three approaches were positively correlated to the reference image with R^2 values between 0.73 and 0.79 for L08-OLI and 0.76 and 0.84 for S2. The best fit between the observed and estimated fractions was yielded by the integrated approach ($R^2 = 0.79$ for L08-OLI and $R^2 = 0.84$ for S2) while the index-based showed less satisfactory performances than the other ones ($R^2 = 0.73$ for L08-OLI and $R^2 = 0.76$ for S2) (Table 4 and Fig. 7).

The highest OA (%), yielded after considering the optimal threshold (OT) values, are also included in table 4. Accordingly, same trend can be observed in performance of different approaches. The highest classification success was achieved by the integrated approach (OA = 76% for L08-OLI and 85% for S2), while the lowest results were obtained while using the spectral indices (OA = 68% for L08-OLI and 74% for S2). Integration of the first and second approaches caused OA enhancement of 8.6% (L08-OLI) and 9% (S2) over the unmixing-based approach, which was much higher than superiority of the unmixing-based approach over the index-based approach (2.9% for L08-OLI and 5.4% for S2).

Table 4. Linear regression parameters and OA (%) (all for bare soil) obtained by different classification approaches

	Index-based		Unmixing-based		Integrated	
	L08-OLI	S2	L08-OLI	S2	L08-OLI	S2
R^2	0.75	0.78	0.77	0.81	0.81	0.87
RMSE	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.01
RPD	2.11	2.13	2.12	2.16	2.15	2.21
OT	NDVI: 0.22 NBR2: 0.13		0.90	0.90	0.85	0.85
OA (%)	68	74	70	78	76	85

OT: optimal threshold, OA: overall accuracy

Fig. 7. Scatter diagrams comparing the observed and estimated bare soil fractions using a) Index-based, b) unmixing-based, and c) integrated approaches (at 400 selected pixels distributed evenly throughout the whole study area)

Fig. 8 displays the bare soil pixels retrieved by applying different classification approaches on the L08-OLI and S2 satellite data. Considering the whole study area, the integrated approach output map had the highest similarity with the reference map so that most of the places considered as the bare soil were correctly detected and less pixels were miss-classified. Classification accuracy was less for other approaches, especially for the index-based approach with the most incorrectly recognized bare and non-bare soil pixels. Comparing the index-based maps and reference images, many bare soil pixels were considered as dry vegetation and vice versa. This was more serious at the northern parts of Nová Ves, whole Jičín, northern and southern parts of Přestavky sites and boundaries of nearly all sites (Fig. 8). Pixels covered by

green vegetation were, however, detected properly by all approaches and successfully separated from the bare soil.

3.4. Remaining bare soil sample-pixels and SOC modeling

Table 5 shows the number of bare soil sample-pixels (n) retrieved by applying each of the three index-based, unmixing-based and integrated classification approaches on L08-OLI and S2 data. The number of common sample-pixels between satellite images and reference map (correctly classified - S) can also be seen for each approach. In addition, T shows the obtaining optimal threshold values of indices for index-based classification and optimal threshold bare soil fractions for unmixing-based classification. Sample pixels with indices values surpassing the related threshold were considered non-bare. For the unmixing-based approach, conversely, those with lower bare soil fractions than the threshold were regarded as non-bare.

Table 5. Retrieved bare soil sample-pixels based on different classification approaches and optimal threshold values

Data		Index-based		Unmixing based	Integrated	Total bare soil sample-pixels in the reference map =
		NDVI	NBR2			
L08-OLI	T	0.23	0.18	0.76	-	211
	n	191		194	161	
	S	144		147	131	
	S/n	0.75		0.76	0.81	
S2	T	0.21	0.18	0.81	-	211
	n	202		206	174	
	S	155		158	149	
	S/n	0.77		0.77	0.86	

T: Threshold value, n: number of bare soil sample-pixels retrieved, S: number of bare soil sample-pixels in common with the reference map

As evidenced in the table, the correct bare sample-pixels retrieved by applying the unmixing based approach (147 for L08-OLI and 158 for S2) are relatively more than those obtained by the index-based approach (144 for L08-OLI and 155 for S2). Despite this slight superiority, both methods shared a relatively similar accuracy (ratio of correctly retrieved bare soil sample-pixels to all retrieved bare soil sample pixels, S/n: 0.75-0.77). The number of bare soil sample-pixels retrieved by the integration of approaches, whether all or correctly classified, was less compared to when each approach was implemented separately (correctly classified/all: 131/161 for L08-OLI and 149/174 for S2). This was expectable since the integrated approach selected those retrieved

sample-pixels common between the two approaches. Despite the lowest quantity of the extracted bare soil sample-pixels, the highest precision was obtained by the integrated approach (S/n: 0.81 for L08-OLI and 0.86 for S2).

With regards to the satellite data used, the number of correctly extracted bare soil sample-pixels were higher for S2 imagery, regardless of which classification approach was used. The precision was also higher for S2, although this superiority was not that noticeable for the two individual approaches. By integrated approach, however, much higher precision was obtained using the S2 data (S/n: 0.86), compared to what obtained by L08-OLI (S/n: 0.81). The better spatial and spectral resolution of the S2 caused better discrimination of the cover classes and more accurate classifications with lower number of misclassified sample-pixels.

Finally, bare soil sample-pixels retrieved by each of the classification approaches were used for developing the RF models to predict SOC. According to the results (Table 6), models developed on results of the unmixing-based approach performed slightly better than those constructed on the index-based approach outputs. Modeling on the integrated approach results, however, yielded significantly higher prediction accuracies ($R^2 \geq 0.32$, $RMSE \leq 0.25\%$, $RPD \geq 1.38$ for L08-OLI and $R^2 \geq 0.37$, $RMSE \leq 0.22\%$, $RPD \geq 1.63$ for S2). Regardless of the approaches and sites, models developed on the S2 data offered better predictions than those developed on the L08-OLI. The highest prediction performance was obtained for the Přebavky site ($R^2 = 0.63$, $RMSE = 0.1\%$, $RPD = 3.10$) followed by Klučov site ($R^2 = 0.64$, $RMSE = 0.11\%$, $RPD = 1.63$) both using the S2 data. That was while the SOC quantification on L08-OLI could reach $R^2 = 0.60$, $RMSE = 0.13\%$ and $RPD = 2.38$ at best. Higher spatial and spectral resolution of S2 images led to establishing more informative relationships between the soil spectra and SOC and hence better performance of the RF models.

Fig. 8. Bare soil pixels retrieved using different classification approaches on L08-OLI and S2 satellite data

Fig. 8. Continue

Table 6. SOC prediction performance of models developed on bare soil sample-pixels retrieved via different classification approaches (validation data)

Site	Approach	Landsat 8-OLI						Sentinel-2					
		n	ME	RMSE	R ²	CCC	RPD	n	ME	RMSE	R ²	CCC	RPD
Nová Ves	Index-based	58	0.15	0.31	0.29	0.32	1.47	61	0.13	0.28	0.32	0.38	1.62
	Unmixing	59	-0.10	0.28	0.27	0.30	1.61	63	0.11	0.25	0.31	0.42	1.83
	Integrated	50	-0.12	0.25	0.32	0.34	1.82	52	-0.08	0.22	0.37	0.39	2.06
Jičín	Index-based	17	-0.12	0.22	0.37	0.41	1.16	19	-0.1	0.19	0.43	0.49	1.35
	Unmixing	18	0.14	0.19	0.46	0.53	1.35	20	0.12	0.21	0.49	0.51	1.22
	Integrated	15	-0.09	0.17	0.51	0.62	1.51	17	0.06	0.14	0.52	0.55	1.83
Klučov	Index-based	56	0.09	0.20	0.50	0.56	0.90	59	-0.06	0.16	0.55	0.62	1.12
	Unmixing	56	0.10	0.17	0.53	0.55	1.05	58	-0.09	0.14	0.58	0.60	1.28
	Integrated	44	-0.07	0.13	0.58	0.62	1.38	50	0.07	0.11	0.64	0.67	1.63
Přestavlky	Index-based	60	0.10	0.23	0.46	0.52	1.35	63	0.08	0.17	0.55	0.61	1.82
	Unmixing	61	0.08	0.16	0.57	0.59	1.94	65	-0.06	0.18	0.59	0.65	1.72
	Integrated	52	-0.04	0.13	0.60	0.63	2.38	55	0.05	0.10	0.63	0.69	3.10
All areas	Index-based	191	-0.16	0.25	0.33	0.37	1.42	202	0.14	0.27	0.24	0.41	1.32
	Unmixing	194	0.09	0.30	0.32	0.32	1.18	206	0.12	0.29	0.33	0.37	1.22
	Integrated	161	0.11	0.23	0.36	0.40	1.54	174	-0.08	0.20	0.39	0.42	1.78

n: number of retrieved bare soil sample-pixels

4. Discussion

4.1. Bare soil fraction estimations and classification

The index-based approach yielded less accurate bare soil cover fraction estimations and OA (%) among all the classification approaches (Table 4). This poor performance was due to the basic shortcomings associated with the indices used in the study. Only limited number of bands were employed to form the NDVI and NBR2 indices and hence, many of the informative spectral features could not be captured. The complex non-linear relationships between the red and NIR spectra and the green vegetation and biomass could not be properly explored by the NDVI. Spectral saturation of the vegetation covered pixels happens during some peak seasons can cause some other problems on the NDVI's applicability (Wang et al., 2023). Finding the optimal threshold value is another challenge when using the indices. Even though the NDVI threshold of 0.25 is widely recognized, this study suggested stricter values of 0.23 (L08-OLI) and 0.21 (S2) to exclude the green vegetation. Some literature, on the other hand, has proposed conservative values of 0.30 (Safanelli et al., 2020) and 0.35 (Castaldi et al., 2019).

The S2 and L08-OLI bands used for calculation of NBR2 are broad, while the dry vegetation related spectral features are very narrow (Nagler et al., 2003). Moreover, those bands are affected by other soil parameters such as moisture and clay minerals (Daughtry and Hunt, 2008; Castaldi et al., 2021), causing significant limitations in discrimination abilities of NBR2 (Dvorakova et al., 2020). The detection potential of NBR2 is also very much dependent on tillage condition of the area and hence, it cannot properly recognize the dry vegetation related to no-tillage (Solano-Correa et al., 2019). This has caused challenges, especially for L08-OLI data with coarser spatial resolution and possibly mixed pixels. In literature, the variation of optimal thresholds for NBR2 has been even higher than NDVI. Demattê et al. (2018) observed the best association between laboratory and Landsat 5 data in Brazil with the threshold value of 0.075, while Vaudour et al. (2021) suggested a stricter value of 0.053 for the S2 data acquired from the Versailles Plain in France. In the study of improving SOC estimation on S2 data, Castaldi et al. (2019) found indirect correlations between the models' accuracy and NBR2 thresholds and that the optimal threshold range of 0.125 to 0.175 could represent a proper trade-off between estimation accuracy and

spatial coverage of the maps. Despite above-mentioned variations, the optimal threshold value was 0.18 for both L08-OLI and S2 data.

The unmixing approach excelled the index-based approach on both fraction estimation and classifications tasks. It might mainly be due to the spectral unmixing uses all of the wavebands to explore the impact of each soil covers class onto every pixel's spectra (Pacheco and McNairn, 2010). To leverage all available bands data, enough samples are usually needed. Even though using small dataset made this study resource-efficient, the unmixing output bare/non-bare soil maps contained some dry vegetation covered pixels mis-classified as bare soil and vice versa. Similar findings have been reported by Pacheco and McNairn (2010). Superiority of the spectral unmixing on indices was also evident on classification of the fields' boundary pixels (Fig. 8). Despite what was mentioned above, the bare sample-pixels extraction accuracy of the two approaches were nearly the same (Table 5).

The integrated approach yielded the most accurate bare soil fraction estimations and OA (%) for both satellite images (table 4). It can be explained by the capability of the integrated approach on leveraging the advantages of the other approaches which boosts its performance. The RF models, developed on outputs of index-based and unmixing-based approaches, had a great role in this success by exploring the complicated relationship between index values and endmember abundances of each pixel and real soil cover fraction values. According to table 5, the integrated approach could recognize the lowest amount of bare soil sample-pixels, with the highest accuracy of 81 (L08-OLI) and 86% (S2), respectively.

With regards to the data types used, the linear regression parameters and OA (%) were higher for S2 than L08-OLI, regardless of the classification approach. One convenient reason can be the higher spatial and spectral resolution of S2, especially within the SWIR region, making it more powerful in detection of the specific spectral features related to dry vegetation. Especially for the index-based approach, the S2 related SWIR wavebands were narrower than the L08-OLI ones, and hence could have a more precise detection of lignin and cellulose absorption features (Hively et al., 2018). This could assist in more successful extraction of the bare soil pixels. Similar bare soil detection superiorities of S2 over L08-OLI have frequently been reported in literature. The higher

performance of S2 over L08-OLI was more evident when applying the integrated approach, so that the best bare soil fraction estimations were achieved by combined implementation of integrated approach and S2 data. The retrieved bare sample-pixels showed similar trend and regardless of the classification approach, higher quantity of bare sample-pixels was retrieved on S2, compared to L08-OLI. The accuracy of bare sample-pixels extracted on S2 data was also higher for all approaches, though, it was not that evident for index and unmixing-based classification approaches.

4.2. SOC modeling and prediction

Better prediction of SOC using outputs of the integrated approach (Table 6) was mainly because the surface reflectance data used was more related to the bare soil than the dry and green vegetation. This was despite the lower quantity of the sample-pixels used for developing the prediction models (for integrated approach) and hence proved the higher importance of the data quality compared to its quantity. The higher quantity of the sample-pixels extracted by the LSU method presumably caused the higher SOC prediction performance of the unmixing-based approach compared to the index-based approach. The better predictions of soil properties on the data retrieved by the unmixing based approach has also been reported in other studies (Pacheco and McNairn, 2010; Laamrani et al., 2020).

In addition, SOC predictions on the S2 data were more successful than those performed on the L08-OLI. These results were expected as the consequence of better classification and bare soil retrieval performance of the S2 data mentioned in previous sections.

Despite the capability of single-date satellite data, acquired close to the sampling date, in prediction of SOC content of the agricultural sites, many pixels might be covered by clouds or green and dry vegetation. This may cause lack of enough sample-pixels needed for the modeling and prediction. One possible solution can be stacking the multitemporal imagery into a single composite image devoid of vegetation covered pixels (Žižala et al., 2022; Vaudour et al., 2022; Castaldi et al., 2023). Some soil parameters may, however, change as the time passes or due to some soil disturbances such as raining, tillage and fertilizing. To face and record these changes,

regular field campaigns can be held in accordance with the satellite acquisition dates, especially during the pre-planting periods.

5. Conclusions

In this study, the index-based and unmixing-based approaches were implemented separately and in combination for soil cover classification and retrieving bare soil pixels of single-date L08-OLI and S2 satellite images. Separate implementation of the approaches yielded lower accuracy results, due to inherent deficiency of multispectral satellite images in discriminating the spectral behavior of bare soil and dry vegetation mixed pixels. This deficiency was exacerbated by implementation of the index-based approach on L08-OLI, when NBR2 sensitivity to the moisture and clay content combined with the low spectral resolution of L08-OLI. Integration of the two approaches, however, could partially solve the problem by enhancing capabilities on separation of the bare soil and dry vegetation. According to the regression analysis, integrated approach showed the best performance in estimation of the bare soil fractions, especially on S2 data (R^2 : 0.87 and RMSE: 0.01). Similarly, the OA of binary classification was the highest for integrated approach reaching 85%, followed by the unmixing-based approach with OA value of 78% (both on S2 data). Considering extraction of the bare soil sample-pixels, integrated approach yielded the lowest quantity with however, the highest accuracy of 0.81 and 0.86 for L08-OLI and S2, respectively. In the meantime, the unmixing-based approach determined the most sample-pixels as bare soil with lower accuracy of 0.76 and 0.77 for L08-OLI and S2, respectively. These variations on the retrieved sample-pixels caused different performances of the SOC prediction models. Accordingly, models developed on the sample-pixels retrieved using the integrated approach showed superior performance followed by those constructed on unmixing-based approach related data. Despite all achievements on production of more accurate bare soil maps, some limitations of the single-date strategy remained still challenging, such as finding proper satellite imagery with low cloud and vegetation cover and minimum time distance from the sampling campaigns.

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Highlights:

- The best bare soil fractions estimations were obtained when integrating the index and unmixing-based approaches.
- Binary bare/non-bare soil maps produced by the integrated approach were the most accurate.
- SOC prediction models performed best on sample-pixels retrieved by the integrated approach.
- Average of the prediction errors was the highest when using the index-based approach.
- S2 data yielded superior classification and prediction accuracies than L08-OLI.